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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LAMIVUDINE AND DOLUTEGRAVIR IN DRUG PRODUCT BY RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

New Analytical method was developed for the estimation of Lamivudine and Dolutegravir in drug product by liquid chromatography. The chromatographic separation was achieved on C18 column (Eclipse XDB-Phenyl 250*4.6mm) at ambient temperature. The separation achieved employing a mobile phase consists of 0.1%v/v Trifluoro acetic acid in water: Methanol (300:700). The flow rate was 1.0ml/ minute and ultra violet detector at 260m. The average retention time for Lamivudine and Dolutegravir found to be 2.412 min and 3.263 min. the proposed method was validated for selectivity, precision, linearity and accuracy. All validation parameters were within the acceptable range. The assay methods were found to be linear from 300.0 – 900.0µg/ml for Lamivudine and 50.0 -150.0µg/ml of Dolutegravir.

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INTRODUCTION

LAMIVUDINE

Lamivudine^[1-2] commonly called 3TC, is an antiretroviral medication used to prevent and treat HIV/AIDS. It is also used to treat chronic hepatitis B when other options are not possible. It is effective against both HIV-1 and HIV-2. It is typically used in combination with other antiretrovirals such as zidovudine and abacavir. Lamivudine may be included as part of post-exposure prevention in those who have been potentially exposed to HIV. Lamivudine is taken by mouth as a liquid or tablet.

Lamivudine is chemically designated as 4-Amino-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-2-one. Its molecular formula is C₈H₁₁N₃O₃S and its molecular weight is 229.26 g/mol

Structure of Lamivudine.

DOLUTEGRAVIR

Dolutegravir (DTG)^[3-4] is a medication used for the treatment of HIV infection. Dolutegravir is an integrase inhibitor. The drug is marketed as Tivicay^[2] by GlaxoSmithKline (GSK). Dolutegravir is approved for use in a broad population of HIV-infected patients. It can be used to treat HIV-infected adults who have never taken HIV therapy (treatment-naïve) and HIV-infected adults who have previously taken HIV therapy (treatment-experienced), including those who have been treated with other integrase strand transfer inhibitors. Tivicay is also approved for children ages 12 years and older weighing at least 40 kilograms (kg) who are treatment-naïve or treatment-experienced but have not previously taken other integrase strand transfer inhibitors.

Dolutegravir is chemically designated as (4R,12aS)-N-(2,4-difluorobenzyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6,8-dioxo-3,4,6,8,12,12a-hexahydro-2H-pyrido[1',2':4,5]pyrazino[2,1-b][1,3]oxazine-9-carboxamide. Its molecular formula is C₂₀H₁₉F₂N₃O₅, and its molecular weight is 419.38 g/mol.

Structure of Dolutegravir.

EXPERIMENTAL:

Equipments:

The chromatographic technique performed on a waters 2695 with 2487 detector and Empower2 software, reversed phase C18 column (Eclipse XDB-Phenyl 250*4.6,5μ) as stationary phase, Ultrasonic cleaner, Scaletech analytical balance, Vacuum micro filtration unit with 0.45μ membrane filter was used in the study.

Materials:

Pharmaceutically pure sample of Lamivudine/Dolutegravir were obtained as gift samples from Fortune pharma training institute, sri sai nagar colony, KPHB, Hyderabad, India.

HPLC-grade Methanol was from qualigens reagents pvt ltd. Trifluoro acetic acid (AR grade) was from sd fine chem.

Chromatographic conditions

The sample separation was achieved on a (5 μ , 250 cm X 4.6 mm i.d.) Eclipse XDB-Phenyl C18 column, aided by mobile phase mixture of 0.1% v/v Trifluoro acetic acid in water: Methanol (30:70). The flow rate was 0.8 ml/ minute and ultra violet detector at 260nm, that was filtered and degassed prior to use, Injection volume is 5 μ l and ambient temperatures.

Preparation of mobile phase:**Buffer Preparation:**

Taken accurately 1ml of Trifluoro acetic acid in 1000mL of water

Mobile phase:

Then added 30 volumes of buffer and 70 volumes of Methanol mixed well and sonicated for 5 min.

Diluent:

Water: Acetonitrile 50:50 v/v

Preparation of standard stock solution:

A 150 mg of pure Lamivudine and 25 mg of Dolutegravir were weighed and transferred to 25 ml of volumetric flask and dissolved in diluent. The flask was shaken and volume was made up to mark with diluent to give a primary stock solution. From the above solution 0.4ml of solution is pipette out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to mark with water to give a solution containing 600 μ g/ml of Lamivudine and 100 μ g/ml Dolutegravir .

Preparation of sample solution:

Accurately weighed twenty tablets were ground to obtain fine powder equivalent to 150mg of Lamivudine and 25mg of Dolutegravir sample were weighed and transferred to 25 ml of volumetric flask and dissolved in diluent. The flask was shaken and volume was made up to mark with diluent to give a primary stock solution. From the above solution 0.4 ml of solution is pipette out into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to mark with diluents to give a solution containing 600 μ g/ml of Lamivudine and 100 μ g/ml Dolutegravir .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:**Determination Of Working Wavelength (λ max):**

10 mg of the Lamivudine and Dolutegravir standard drug is taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in Diluent and volume made up to the mark, from this solution 0.1 ml is pipette into 10 ml volumetric flask and made upto the mark with the Water to give a concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The above prepared solution is scanned in uv between 200-400 nm using Water as blank. The λ max was found to be 260nm

After several initial trails with mixtures of methanol, water, ACN and buffer in various combinations and proportions, a trail with a mobile phase mixture of 0.1% v/v TFA in water: Methanol (30:70). The flow rate was 1.0 ml/ minute brought sharp peaks. The chromatogram was shown in Figure-1.

Figure.1 Chromatogram of Lamivudine/Dolutegravir.

METHOD VALIDATION:**Linearity:**

Linearity was studied by analyzing five standard solutions covering the range of 300.0 -900.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Lamivudine and 50.0 -150.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Dolutegravir. From the primary stock solution 0.5ml,0.75ml,1.0ml,1.25ml,1.5 ml of aliquots are pipette into 10 ml volumetric flasks and made up to the mark with the water to give a concentrations of 300.0 $\mu\text{g /mL}$, 450.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$,600.0 $\mu\text{g/ML}$,750.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 900.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Lamivudine and 50.0g/mL,75.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$,100.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$,125.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 150.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ Dolutegravir. Calibration curve with concentration versus peak areas was plotted by injecting the above prepared solutions and the obtained data were subjected to regression analysis using the least squares method.

Table. 1: Linearity data of Lamivudine.

Level	Concentration (mg/mL)	Peak area
50%	0.300	1000569
75%	0.450	1431355
100%	0.600	1851581
125%	0.750	2194208
150%	0.900	2607788

Figure.2: Linearity (calibration) curve of Lamivudine.**Table .2: Linearity data of Dolutegravir.**

Level	Concentration (mg/mL)	Peak area
50%	0.050	717514
75%	0.075	1036839
100%	0.100	1356301
125%	0.125	1676495
150%	0.150	2043118

Figure .3: Linearity (calibration) curve of Dolutegravir.

RESULT

A linear relationship between peak areas versus concentrations was observed for Lamivudine and Dolutegravir in the range of 50% to 150% of nominal concentration. Correlation coefficient was 0.9993 and 0.9996 for both Lamivudine and Dolutegravir which prove that the method is linear in the range of 50% to 150%.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification:

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were separately determined based on standard deviation of the y-intercept and the slope of the calibration curve by using the equations (1) and (2), respectively.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma / S \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma / S \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where,

σ = the standard deviation of the response (STEYX)

S = the slope of the calibration curve

The slope S may be estimated from the calibration curve of the analyte.

Table .3: LOD and LOQ values Calculated from calibration curve:

Parameter	Lamivudine mg	Dolutegravir mg
LOD	0.034	0.004
LOQ	0.103	0.013

Method precision (repeatability)

The precision of the method was checked by repeated preparation (n=6) of 600.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Lamivudine and 100.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Dolutegravir without changing the parameter of the proposed chromatographic method. And measure the peak areas and retention times.

Table.4: Summary of peak areas for method precision of Lamivudine.

Sample No	Retention time	Peak area	% Assay
1	2.412	1821825	99.7
2	2.411	1816004	99.6
3	2.412	1820231	99.4
4	2.408	1826610	99.5
5	2.412	1839151	100.6
6	2.411	1879371	100.0
Mean	2.411	1833865	99.8
%RSD	0.06	1.29	0.46

Table.5: Summary of peak areas for method precision of Dolutegravir.

Sample No	Retention time	Peak area	% Assay
1	3.255	1330362	99.3
2	3.254	1329341	98.9
3	3.256	1363551	99.0
4	3.254	1340479	99.7
5	3.255	1354959	99.8
6	3.252	1366042	98.6
Mean	3.254	1347456	99.2
%RSD	0.04	1.21	0.46

RESULT

Results of variability were summarized in the above table. Percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) was found to be less than 2.0% which proves that method is precise.

Accuracy (recovery study):

The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating the recoveries of Lamivudine and Dolutegravir by analyzing solutions containing approximately 50%, 100% and 150% of the working strength of Lamivudine and Dolutegravir. The percentage recovery results obtained are listed in Table 6 & 7

Table .6: Recovery data of Lamivudine.

LEVEL	S.NO	%Recovery of Lamivudine	Average
50	1	99.4	99.3%
	2	99.8	
	3	98.8	
100	1	99.7	99.5%
	2	99.6	
	3	99.4	
150	1	99.3	99.6%
	2	99.7	
	3	99.8	

Table .7: Recovery data of Dolutegravir.

Level	S.NO	%Recovery of Dolutegravir	Average
50	1	99.5	99.8%
	2	99.4	
	3	100.4	
100	1	99.3	99.1%
	2	98.9	
	3	99.0	
150	1	99.8	99.9%
	2	100.2	
	3	99.8	

RESULT

Results of accuracy study are presented in the above table. All the results indicate that the method is highly accurate.

Robustness:

Robustness is the measure of a method remain unaffected by small, deliberate changes in method parameters like flow rate and detection wavelength on assay of the analyte of interest. Here the detection wavelength varied ± 2 nm and flow rate was varied ± 0.2 ml/min. The results were shown in (Table no. 8&9)

Table .8: Results of Lamivudine.

Parameter	Rt of Lamivudine	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry
Decreased flow rate (0.7ml/min)	2.998	9738	1.12
Increased flow rate (0.9ml/min)	2.016	7368	1.06
Wave Length	2.413	8267	1.07
258nm			
262nm	2.414	8342	1.07

Table .9: Results of Dolutegravir.

Parameter	Rt of Dolutegravir	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry
Decreased flow rate (0.7ml/min)	4.051	13074	1.08
Increased flow rate (0.9ml/min)	2.718	10551	1.06
Wave Length	3.255	11729	1.09
258nm			
262nm	3.257	11729	1.09

RESULT

The results of Robustness of the present method had shown that changes are not significant we can say that the method is Robust.

Ruggedness:

The ruggedness of the method was studied by analyzing the sample and standard preparations by two analysts. The results were shown in Table no.10&11.

Table .10: Results of Lamivudine.

		%Assay	%RSD
Analyst-1	LAMIVUDINE	99.7	0.07%
Analyst-2		99.6	

Table .11: Results of Dolutegravir.

		%Assay	%RSD
Analyst-1	DOLUTEGRAVIR	99.2	0.14%
Analyst-2		99.4	

RESULT

The %RSD assay values between two analysts was calculated, this indicates the method was rugged.

Table .12: Summary of Lamivudine.

S.NO	Parameter	Result	Acceptance criteria
1	System suitability		
	Theoretical plates	2.413	Not less than 2000
	Asymmetry	8353	Not more than 2.0
	Retention time	1.07	
	%RSD	1.03	Not more than 2.0
2	Specificity	Specific	Specific
3	Method precision(%RSD)	1.29	Not more than 2.0%
4	Linearity Range(mcg/ml)	300.0- 900.0	
	Correlation coefficient(r^2)	0.9993	Not less than 0.990
5	Accuracy (Mean % recovery)		97 - 103%
	50%	99.3	
	100%	99.5	
	150%	99.6	
6	Robustness	All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.	

*RSD = Relative standard deviation.

Table .13: Summary of Dolutegravir.

S.NO	Parameter	Result	Acceptance criteria
1	System suitability		
	Theoretical plates	3.256	Not less than 2000
	Asymmetry	11802	Not more than 2.0
	Retention time	1.09	
	%RSD	1.03	Not more than 2.0
2	Specificity	Specific	Specific
3	Method precision(%RSD)	0.21	Not more than 2.0%
4	Linearity Range(mcg/ml)	50.0- 150.0	
	Correlation coefficient(r^2)	0.9996	Not less than 0.990
5	Accuracy (Mean % recovery)		97 - 103%
	50%	99.8	
	100%	99.1	
	150%	99.9	
6	Robustness	All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.	

CONCLUSION

From the above experimental results it was concluded that, this newly developed method for the simultaneous estimation of LAMIVUDINE and DOLUTEGRAVIR was found to be simple, precise, accurate and high resolution and shorter retention time makes this method more acceptable and cost effective and it can be effectively applied for routine analysis in research institutions, quality control department in meant in industries, approved testing laboratories.

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